

Potential risk of organochlorine contamination to human health in Wonosobo district

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ABSTRACT

A risk assessment of organochlorine contamination was undertaken a rice field in Serayu upper watershed of Wonosobo District. This study aims to assess the potential non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risks that the community must face, specifically the contamination of organochlorine residues in soil and crop yields being consumed. The risk assessment methodology is based on that devised by the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR). Soil and plant samples from paddy fields in Wonosobo District were extracted using the SNI 06-6990.1-2004 method, and then measured using GC Shimadzu. Results showed there were potential carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks due to soil contaminated by residues of organochlorine Lindane, Heptachlor, Aldrin, Chlordane, Toxaphene, Dieldrin, DDT, Endrin, Endosulfan, and Mirex. There is a potential risk through oral exposure when people consume celery leaves and leeks, and both foodstuffs were found to contain dieldrin and lindane, aldrin, and chlordane. Conversely, rice produced from rice fields was free of any organochlorine content. According to the ASTDR classification, the paddy fields in Wonosobo District will need to be better monitored in the future.

Key words: organochlorine, paddy fields, risk assessment

INTRODUCTION

Population and economic growth, increased purchasing power, and changes in people's tastes are triggering greater demands and varieties of food. However, food supply is under threat of stagnating or declining due to production problems (Maulana et al., 2016; Irawan, 2016). To increase production totals, farmers tend to use shortcuts through the excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides. This has an impact on the accumulation of pesticide residues in the soil. There are certain organochlorine pesticides that are accumulated and persistent in rice fields and rivers (Ardiwinata and Nursyamsi, 2012; Mulyadi et al., 2014). ASTDR (2013) has included organochlorine pesticides as harmful compounds because they are accumulative and remain persistent in the soil (WHO, 2007). Organochlorine pesticides have been banned for use but some developing countries, including Indonesia, still use these

pesticides because they are relatively cheap, effective and in plentiful supply (Rahmawati et al, 2017).

Modern agricultural technology is spurring the productivity of strategic agricultural commodities, including the use of agrochemical materials (fertilizers and pesticides). However, excessive use of pesticides can cause large volumes of residues to emerge on the land and the surrounding environment. As a consequence of intensive use of pesticides, the need for agrochemicals, especially pesticides, is also increasing every year. This is evidenced by the distribution of pesticides in Indonesia, based on data from the Directorate of Fertilizers and Pesticides. It emerged that the number of pesticide formulas registered and circulating in Indonesia in 2006 was around 1,336 whereas a decade later in 2016 there were 3,207 formulas (Direktorat Pupuk dan Pestisida, 2016). It has been suggested that climate change will contribute to the rising use of pesticide use by around 60% by the year 2100 (Koleva et al., 2009).

Pesticides can help communities to remove or eradicate pests, but on the other hand are dangerous to all creatures that are not even the primary target, and they are proven to be very dangerous to people's health. The negative impacts caused by pesticide residues on human health include (Riza and Gayatri, 1994): cancer (carcinogenic), birth defects (teratogenic), nerve damage (neurotoxic), genetic mutations (mutagenic), immune system disorders, and destruction of or damage to the reproductive and endocrine systems (EDs, Endocrine Disrupting Pesticides). Responding to the dangers of pesticide residues in the environment and food, researchers in several countries have assiduously assessed pesticide residue contamination, for example: Farina et al., (2016) in agricultural soils and its health assessment for humans in the Cameron highlands, Malaysia; Al-Daghri et al., (2018) who undertook biomonitoring and risk assessment of organochlorine pesticides among Saudi adults; Wei et al., (2015) who investigated residual levels of organochlorine pesticides in north-western China; Koranteng et al., (2017) who examined residues and undertook a risk assessment of organochlorine pesticides in Ghana; and Rahmawati (2016), whose study involved a risk analysis of organochlorine pesticides residue in West Java, Indonesia.

At the present time, food quality and safety are important issues throughout the world, including Indonesia. Consumers are more selective in choosing their food which ideally should be high in nutrients and free from pesticide residues. This has led to increased demand for organic products. The objectives of this study are to: (1) investigate organochlorine residues and their levels in soil, plants (rice, celery and leek); (2) compare the daily intake obtained by Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) and Maximum Residue Limit (MRL); and (3) analyze the risk of organochlorine exposure in local communities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling and research area

The research area includes paddy fields in the Serayu Watershed, Wonosobo District. The number of soil samples is 319 involving rice, celery and leek. Soil sampling is carried out in the processing layer (0-20 cm) by composing 3-5 subsamples of soil with a radius of 50 meters, as much as 1 kg. Examples of rice, celery or leek are taken at a soil sample of 0.5 kg. A map of the research location is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Location of soil and plant sampling

Determination of the Impact of Organochlorines

People affected by organochlorine contamination are divided into two types: firstly, the potential for being affected by contact with the soil; and secondly, those eating food produced in the area. Two age groups were determined to measure the exposure dose: 12 years or younger, taking into account an average weight of 30 kg; and 13 years and over, taking into account an average weight of 60 kg. This is also needed to calculate food consumption and frequency and duration of exposure. Intake is estimated to assume rice, celery and leek are 114.6 kg / capita / year, 7.3 kg / capita / year and 12.05 kg / capita / year, respectively. Exposure is considered to be continuous throughout the course of a person's life.

The estimated exposure dose for contaminants that is present in the soil and food (consumption) employs the following formula (USEPA, 2011):

1. Estimated dose of soil exposure (ED_{si})

$$ED_{si} = \frac{C \cdot IR \cdot EF \cdot 10^{-6}}{BW}$$

where, C = the concentration of contaminants in the soil (mg/kg); IR = rate of absorption of soil; EF = exposure factor; BW = weight. Standard value (ATSDR): adult – 50 mg/day; children - 50 to 200 mg/day.

2. Estimated consumption dose of contaminated food (ED_f)

$$ED_f = \frac{C \cdot R_i \cdot EF}{BW}$$

where, C = the concentration of contaminants in the food group i (mg/g); R_i = group food intake level i (g/day); EF = exposure factor; BW = weight. Estimated doses are then compared with parameters that indicate the level of health risk.

3. Estimated total exposure dose (ED_t)

$$ED_t = ED_{si} + ED_f$$

The potential risk of organisms to human health is divided into two, namely, those who are non-carcinogenic (not cancer-causing) and carcinogenic. The potential risk of non-carcinogenic organochlorine is measured using the value of Hazard Quotient (HQ) with the equation,

$$HQ = \frac{ED_t}{RfD}$$

Where, the RfD is an estimate of the maximum daily dose intake allowed. If the HQ value is <1, then the potential health risk is low, while HQ > 1 is used if the risk to health is high. The risk of heavy metal intake for both values is calculated using a hazard index (HI), which is assumed to be the cumulative effect of all heavy metals evaluated, using the equation,

$$HI = \sum HQ$$

If the HI <1 then the chronic risk of organochlorine is rare, whereas if HI is ≥ 1 then the risk is more common.

Cancer risk (CR) is calculated using the multiplication between daily intake and slope factor (SF) for cancer. The risk of cancer is thought to be a long process that an individual may suffer from at some point in his or her life. For example, if the CR value is 10⁻⁴ this shows that 1 in 10,000 individuals develop cancer. Cancer risk value is calculated using the following equation,

$$CR = ED_t \cdot SF$$

$$CR_t = \sum CR$$

If the elements that have the potential to trigger cancer are more than one then the potential is accumulated. The risk of cancer ranging from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻⁴ is possible.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Concentration of Organochlorines in Soil

The concentration of organochlorine in soil at Wonosobo District's rice fields is shown in Table 1. The average values of all assessed organochlorines, namely, lindane, heptachlor, chlordane, toxaphene, dieldrin, endrin and DDT were above the maximum allowable limits, while aldrin and mirex were below the limit permitted. Some of the soil samples contain all organochlorine pesticides with a value above the allowed limit.

Table 1. Concentration of Organochlorines in Soil at paddy rice fields in Wonosobo district

organochlorine	detected	min (mg/kg)	max (mg/kg)	mean ± SD (mg/kg)	MTR* (mg/kg)	Reference value intervention*
Lindane	25	0,00689	0,13623	0,0141 ± 0,0255	0,01	1,2
Heptachlor	48	0,00001	0,31651	0,0120 ± 0,0285	0,039	4
Aldrin	18	0,00052	0,04123	0,0069 ± 0,0070	0,029	0,32
Chlordane	9	0,03816	0,25115	0,0581 ± 0,0245	0,05	4
Endosulfan	57	0,00109	7,89198	0,0034 ± 0,0027	0,0085	4
Toxaphene	13	0,13457	7,14248	0,8908 ± 1,9047	0,5	-
Dieldrin	43	0,00031	1,04223	0,0551 ± 0,0870	0,011	-
Endrin	37	0,00071	0,10498	0,0096 ± 0,0164	0,0075	-
DDT	21	0,00095	0,40203	0,0231 ± 0,0870	0,015	1,7
Mirex	24	0,00132	0,02547	0,0057 ± 0,0061	0,027	-

MTR: maximum tolerable risk, * Asmus et al (2008)

The residual content of organochlorine pesticide detected in succession from large to small in Wonosobo district is Toxapene>Chlordane > Dieldrin> DDT> Lindane > Heptachlor> Endrin> Aldrin> Mirex> Endosulfan. Heptachlor, endosulfan, Dieldrin and Endrin were detected in more than 10% of the total samples and dieldrin were detected above the most BMR. Dieldrin and DDT found in Wonosobo District rice fields have the potential to occur cross resistance if farmers apply pyrethroids, because cross-resistance will occur between organochlorine groups (Dieldrin and DDT) with pyrethroid groups (Hemingway, 1997).

Concentration of Organochlorines in rice and vegetables

The concentration of organochlorine in rice and vegetables at Wonosobo District's rice fields is shown in Table 2. No organochlorines were found in all rice and cabbage samples. Whereas in the celery sample found dieldrin and in the sample of leeks found aldrin and chlordane compounds, where the content of the chlordane above the maximum residue limits.

Table 2. Concentration of Organochlorines in rice and vegetables at paddy rice fields in Wonosobo district

organochlorine	concentration (mg/kg)				BMR (mg/kg)*
	rice	celery	Leek	Cabbage	
Lindane	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0,5
Heptachor	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0,05
Aldrin	<LOD	<LOD	0,00615	<LOD	0,1
Chlordane	<LOD	<LOD	0,05751	<LOD	0,02
Endosulfan	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2
Toxaphene	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2
Dieldrin	<LOD	0,05122	<LOD	<LOD	0,1
Endrin	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0,05
DDT	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1
Mirex	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1

*SNI 7313: 2008

Estimated exposure dose from contaminated soil and food

Organochlorines exposure from contaminated soil and food is presented in Tables 3 and 4. The intake (ED) of contaminated soil is greater what is found in the food. The intake (ED) of food was only detected in aldrin, dieldrin and chlordane compounds. The risk of children being exposed to them is higher than that of adults.

Table 3. Estimated exposure dose from organochlorine contaminated soil

organochlorine	concentration (ug/kg)	IR (child)	IR (adult)	EF (child)	EF (adult)	BW (child)	BW (adult)	ED (child)	ED (adult)
Lindane	14,1	0,2	0,05	0,08	0,08	30	60	0,007	0,001
Heptachor	12	0,2	0,05	0,15	0,15	30	60	0,012	0,002
Aldrin	6,9	0,2	0,05	0,06	0,06	30	60	0,003	0,000
Chlordane	58,1	0,2	0,05	0,03	0,03	30	60	0,011	0,001
Endosulfan	3,4	0,2	0,05	0,18	0,18	30	60	0,004	0,001
Toxaphene	890,8	0,2	0,05	0,04	0,04	30	60	0,242	0,030
Dieldrin	55,1	0,2	0,05	0,13	0,13	30	60	0,050	0,006
Endrin	9,6	0,2	0,05	0,12	0,12	30	60	0,007	0,001
DDT	23,1	0,2	0,05	0,07	0,07	30	60	0,010	0,001
Mirex	5,7	0,2	0,05	0,08	0,08	30	60	0,003	0,000

Rahmawati et al., (2017) in their research with carrot and potato commodities obtained the same pattern where the value of intake (ED) is relatively small. Therefore it does not contribute enough to the magnitude of the hazard index and cancer risk.

Table 4. Estimated exposure dose from food contaminated with organochlorine

organochlorine	concentration (ug/kg)	IR (child)	IR (adult)	EF (child)	EF (adult)	BW (child)	BW (adult)	ED (child)	ED (adult)
Lindane	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000
Heptachor	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000
Aldrin	6,1	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0012	0,0006
Chlordane	57,5	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0110	0,0055
Endosulfan	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000
Toxaphene	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000
Dieldrin	51,2	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0098	0,0049
Endrin	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000
DDT	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000
Mirex	0,0	0,0057	0,0057	1	1	30	60	0,0000	0,0000

Hazard index and cancer risk

Hazard quotient (HQ) from each organochlorine and hazard index (HI) as the total hazard quotient of soil, rice and vegetable samples from this study are described in Table 5. The HQ from soil, rice and vegetables is below the hazard index except dieldrin, whereas the HI value is above the risk limit. These results indicate there may be concerns about the potential for non-cancer outcomes. As a consequence, there are possible chronic effects. In the case of carcinogenic effects, the risk value of each organochlorine is determined by multiplying the intake (ED) with SF (slope factor). Calculations concerning the risk of each organochlorine and the risk of total organochlorine are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Potency of health and cancer risk

Organo-chlorine	Total exposed		RfD	SF	HQ		CR	
	ED (child)	ED (adult)			child	adult	child	adult
Lindane	0,007	0,001	3.10 ⁻⁰⁴	1,1	0,02	0,00	8.1.10 ⁻⁰⁶	1.0.10 ⁻⁰⁶
Heptachor	0,012	0,002	5.10 ⁻⁰⁴	4,5	0,02	0,00	5.4.10 ⁻⁰⁵	6.8.10 ⁻⁰⁶
Aldrin	0,004	0,001	3.10 ⁻⁰⁵	17	0,13	0,03	6.4.10 ⁻⁰⁵	1.5.10 ⁻⁰⁵
Chlordane	0,022	0,007	5.10 ⁻⁰⁴	0,35	0,04	0,01	7.7.10 ⁻⁰⁶	2.4.10 ⁻⁰⁶
Endosulfan	0,004	0,001	6.10 ⁻⁰³	NA	0,00	0,00		
Toxaphene	0,242	0,030	NA	1.1			2.7.10 ⁻⁰⁴	3.3.10 ⁻⁰⁵
Dieldrin	0,059	0,011	5.10 ⁻⁰⁵	16	1,19	0,22	9.5.10 ⁻⁰⁴	1.8.10 ⁻⁰⁴
Endrin	0,007	0,001	3.10 ⁻⁰⁴	NA	0,02	0,00		
DDT	0,010	0,001	5.10 ⁻⁰⁴	0,34	0,02	0,00	3.4.10 ⁻⁰⁶	4.3.10 ⁻⁰⁷
Mirex	0,003	0,000	NA	NA				
HI/CRT					1.4	0.3	1.4.10 ⁻⁰³	2.4.10 ⁻⁰⁴

The hazard index and cancer risk for each organochlorine that is caused by soil exposure is greater than food. Therefore, this risk is greater for workers in agriculture work on the land every day of their lives.

CONCLUSION

1. There are some samples having a concentration of organochlorine in both soil and plants that exceed the allowable limits.
2. Non-carcinogenic risks for children exceed the allowable limits contributed by aldrin contamination, while for adults there is still a permissible threshold ($HI > 1$).
3. Carcinogenic risk for children is $1.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ while for adults it is $2.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$; both are greater than the limit ($CRt > 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$).

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